

Teacher Well-Being and Instructional Sustainability Among Public Secondary School Teachers

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the relationship between teacher well-being and instructional sustainability among public secondary school teachers in Santo Tomas, Isabela. Grounded in the view that the quality and continuity of instruction were shaped not only by professional competence but also by teachers' emotional, social, and work-related condition, the study investigated the levels of teacher well-being and instructional sustainability and determined the predictive influence of well-being dimensions on sustained instructional practice. A cross-sectional predictive-correlational design was employed, and data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and partial least squares structural equation modeling. Findings revealed that teacher

well-being and instructional sustainability were generally at a high level. However, work-related wellness and continuity of teaching practices emerged as the most vulnerable aspects, indicating that teachers remained professionally committed despite experiencing some strain in maintaining consistent instructional delivery over time. The structural model showed that emotional balance, professional satisfaction, social support, and work-related wellness significantly predicted instructional sustainability, with work-related wellness registering the strongest influence. The model further demonstrated moderate to strong predictive relevance, confirming that teacher well-being explained a substantial portion of the variance in instructional sustainability. The study concluded that sustaining classroom instruction depended not only on teachers' commitment and skills but also on the conditions that supported their well-being. It was recommended that schools strengthen wellness-oriented interventions, collegial support systems, and workload-responsive policies to help teachers sustain quality instruction more effectively.

Keywords: *Teacher well-being, instructional sustainability, work-related wellness, professional satisfaction, public secondary school teachers*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers remain at the center of educational quality because they directly shape classroom climate, student engagement, and the continuity of learning. In recent years, however, the conversation on teacher effectiveness has expanded beyond competence and content mastery to include teacher well-being as a necessary condition for sustained instructional practice. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development emphasized that teacher well-being is not a single emotional state but a multidimensional construct that includes physical and mental well-being, cognitive well-being, subjective well-being, and social well-being. It further explained that these dimensions are closely connected to teachers' working conditions and to the quality of teaching that occurs in classrooms (OECD, 2020). This perspective is

important because it recognizes that teachers are more likely to sustain meaningful instruction when they experience supportive environments, manageable demands, and a sense of professional value.

The growing concern for teacher well-being has also become an international educational priority because many school systems are now facing problems related to teacher stress, attrition, and declining professional motivation. UNESCO reported that the global teacher shortage is not simply a staffing issue but a broader crisis connected to motivation, retention, training, working conditions, and social status. It highlighted that strengthening teacher well-being, improving working conditions, and involving teachers in decision-making are essential for attracting and retaining quality educators. UNESCO also noted that the demand for teachers is especially pressing at the secondary level, making the sustainability of teaching practice a serious policy concern for contemporary education systems (UNESCO & International Task Force on Teachers for Education 2030, 2024). These global concerns suggest that instructional sustainability cannot be separated from the human condition of teachers who carry out the daily work of teaching. Teacher well-being has increasingly been linked to desirable school and classroom outcomes. OECD (2020) findings showed that teacher well-being is associated with stress levels, work engagement, commitment to remain in the profession, and the quality of classroom processes. More recent OECD (2025) reporting likewise underscored that teachers with higher well-being tend to report greater self-efficacy, job satisfaction, motivation, and professional commitment, while low well-being may contribute to absenteeism, poor performance, turnover, and reduced instructional quality. In the same line, systematic review evidence concluded that teacher well-being has meaningful relationships with a range of positive outcomes in schools, while a large-scale study cited in that review showed that emotional exhaustion is associated with lower instructional quality and weaker student outcomes (Dreer, 2023; Klusmann et al., 2022). These perspectives indicate that instructional sustainability is not only about keeping programs running over time, but also about preserving the teacher's capacity to teach with consistency, quality, and professional energy. The Department of Education acknowledged in DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024 that administrative tasks had to be removed from public school teachers so they could maximize their time in actual classroom teaching, focus on the teaching and learning process, and have their welfare and well-being protected and uplifted to support them in teaching better. More recently, DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2026 on wellness leave further affirmed that promoting mental health and well-being, strengthening resilience, reducing absenteeism, and improving the quality of public services are organizational priorities for DepEd personnel. These policy directions show that teacher well-being is no longer treated as a private or secondary matter, but as an institutional concern that influences productivity, continuity of service, and educational quality. Health agencies have similarly stressed that schools should support not only learners but also the well-being of school staff. The World Health Organization (2021) explained that mental health in schools has important implications for teachers as well as students, and that educational settings should adopt practical steps that support mental health and well-being across the school community. This view strengthens the argument that sustaining instruction requires conditions in which teachers can remain psychologically, emotionally, and professionally functional. When teachers are overwhelmed by chronic demands, excessive workload, or prolonged stress, the sustainability of their classroom practice may weaken even if curriculum expectations remain unchanged.

In Santo Tomas, Isabela, teachers are expected to respond to instructional demands, learner diversity, school responsibilities, and accountability expectations while maintaining the continuity and quality of teaching. Although policies and international literature increasingly recognize the value of teacher well-being, context-specific inquiry remains necessary to understand how well-being relates to instructional sustainability among public secondary school teachers in an actual school division environment. Examining this relationship can provide a clearer basis for school-based support systems, leadership decisions, and teacher development initiatives that do not only aim for immediate performance, but also for the long-term sustainment of effective teaching. Thus, this study was anchored on the view that teacher well-being is not

merely a personal concern, but a professional and institutional resource that may shape the sustainability of instruction in public secondary schools.

Literature Review

Teacher Well-Being as a Multidimensional Construct

Teacher well-being has increasingly been recognized as a foundational concern in education because it influences how teachers think, feel, relate, and perform in their professional roles. A major contribution to this area came from the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, which conceptualized teachers' occupational well-being as teachers' responses to the cognitive, emotional, health, and social conditions attached to their work and profession. In this framework, teacher well-being includes four interrelated dimensions: cognitive well-being, subjective well-being, physical and mental well-being, and social well-being. This view is important because it frames well-being not as a private personal issue alone, but as a professional condition shaped by school contexts and capable of affecting teaching and learning processes (Viac & Fraser, 2020).

Hascher and Waber (2021), in their systematic review, emphasized that teacher well-being is a complex construct associated with emotional experiences, professional functioning, and contextual conditions in schools. Their review showed that teacher well-being cannot be reduced to the absence of stress alone, since it also involves positive affect, satisfaction, competence, and supportive relationships. In a more recent conceptual review, Kurrle et al. (2025) likewise noted that teacher well-being is increasingly understood as influential not only for teachers themselves but also for school performance and retention. These perspectives support the idea that teacher well-being should be studied as a broad professional resource rather than a narrow emotional condition.

Global Concern for Teacher Well-Being

The concern for teacher well-being has become more urgent because many educational systems are facing teacher shortages, burnout, and declining professional attractiveness. UNESCO reported that the world needs millions of additional teachers by 2030 and that teacher shortages are closely tied to working conditions, support systems, motivation, and well-being. The report particularly noted that secondary education faces a substantial demand for teachers, making teacher support and retention a pressing issue for systems that seek continuity and quality in instruction (UNESCO & International Task Force on Teachers for Education 2030, 2024).

This global concern was further echoed in recent analyses of the teaching profession. OECD's TALIS 2024 results showed that teacher well-being is strongly associated with job satisfaction, self-efficacy, motivation, and commitment to remain in the profession. The same report stressed that employment and working conditions influence teachers' intention to stay more strongly than salary alone. In effect, teacher well-being is no longer viewed as an optional wellness concern, but as an educational issue connected to long-term professional sustainability and the stability of teaching work in schools (OECD, 2025).

Antecedents of Teacher Well-Being

The literature consistently shows that teacher well-being is shaped by the conditions under which teachers work. Viac and Fraser (2020) explained that job demands such as workload, performance pressures, and role complexity may weaken well-being, while job resources such as professional autonomy, collegial support, and opportunities for development may strengthen it. This framing closely reflects the job demands and resources perspective, which helps explain why teachers in the same profession may experience different levels of well-being depending on the supportiveness and burden of their workplace environments.

Empirical studies also highlight the importance of working conditions. Toropova et al. (2021) found that school working conditions, including workload and school environment, are central to teacher job satisfaction. More recent international evidence similarly identified leadership support, student discipline, workload, and professional development as important correlates of teacher job satisfaction across countries (Eryilmaz et al., 2025). Related work on school climate also found that teacher well-being is associated with school climate, partly through the satisfaction of teachers' basic psychological needs, suggesting that the social and organizational environment of the school remains a major influence on well-being.

Teacher emotional regulation and psychological resources also matter. Wang et al. (2024) examined teacher emotional exhaustion and emphasized that exhaustion emerges from a combination of school-related stressors and individual factors. In a related study, Ma et al. (2023) found that teacher emotion regulation and psychological capital were associated with stronger work engagement. These studies suggest that teacher well-being is shaped not only by institutional conditions but also by the teacher's internal coping resources, resilience, and ability to manage emotional demands in the profession.

Teacher Well-Being and Teaching Quality

A strong body of literature supports the claim that teacher well-being is connected to teaching quality. Hascher and Waber (2021) noted that available evidence points to teacher well-being as relevant to teaching effectiveness and student outcomes. Dreer (2023), in a systematic review focused on outcomes of teacher well-being, concluded that teacher well-being is significantly related to desirable educational outcomes, including retention, healthy teacher-student relationships, and student-related outcomes. Although causal evidence remains more limited than correlational evidence, the pattern across studies suggests that teacher well-being has educational consequences beyond the personal lives of teachers.

More direct evidence appears in studies that connect teacher well-being to instructional quality. Klusmann et al. (2022) found that teachers' emotional exhaustion was associated with lower levels of emotional support and classroom organization, and that lower instructional quality partly mediated the link between exhaustion and student outcomes. Similarly, Wartenberg et al. (2023) reported through meta-analytic evidence that teacher job satisfaction is positively related to high-quality teacher-student interactions and other beneficial school outcomes. These findings are especially important for the present study because they show that teacher well-being is not detached from the classroom. Rather, it is reflected in how instruction is delivered, organized, and sustained across time.

Understanding Instructional Sustainability

While the exact phrase *instructional sustainability* is less standardized in the literature than terms such as instructional quality, teacher retention, work engagement, and professional sustainability, related scholarship suggests that it refers to the teacher's capacity to maintain meaningful, effective, and consistent instruction over time. This interpretation is supported by OECD work linking teacher well-being to motivation to continue teaching and to quality learning environments, as well as by UNESCO's emphasis on sustaining the teaching profession through better support and improved working conditions (OECD, 2020; OECD, 2025; UNESCO & International Task Force on Teachers for Education 2030, 2024). This is therefore a reasoned conceptual reading of the literature rather than a single universally fixed definition.

Research and policy discussions increasingly use terms such as sustainable teacher workforce, sustainable professional practice, and sustaining the teaching profession to refer to the long-term capacity of teachers to remain effective, engaged, and committed in their work. OECD's (2025) discussion on sustaining the teaching profession directly connected teachers' career intentions with well-being and job satisfaction. In the same direction, recent scholarship on teacher well-being has argued that it is essential for the sustainable development of teachers, students, and the school community. These ideas closely align with instructional sustainability because sustained instruction depends on teachers who are well enough to continue teaching effectively and responsibly over time (Li et al., 2025).

Work Engagement, Motivation, and Sustained Instruction

Work engagement is another important concept in understanding instructional sustainability. Engaged teachers are more energetic, focused, and invested in their work, which increases the likelihood that instruction remains purposeful and consistent. Ma et al. (2023) found that psychological capital mediated the relationship between teachers' emotion regulation and work engagement, indicating that emotionally supported teachers are more likely to remain engaged in teaching. Huang et al. (2023) also found that personal growth initiative was related to teacher engagement and instructional quality, suggesting that teachers who remain development-oriented are more capable of sustaining strong classroom practice.

The same line of thinking appears in recent studies of instructional emotions and performance. Dilekçi et al. (2025) reported that work engagement mediated the relationship between positive instructional emotions and job performance. Although this work did not use the term instructional sustainability directly, it supports the broader idea that emotionally healthy and engaged teachers are better positioned to perform their work effectively. Thus, the literature suggests that instructional sustainability may be strengthened when teachers maintain motivation, positive professional emotions, and strong engagement with teaching.

Philippine Policy

In the Philippines, teacher well-being has gained clearer policy recognition. DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2024 mandated the immediate removal of administrative tasks from public school teachers in order to allow them to focus more on the teaching and learning process and to support and protect their welfare and well-being. This policy is directly relevant to the present study because it recognizes that the burden of non-teaching work can weaken teachers' ability to sustain quality classroom instruction.

Recent Philippine policy developments further show that teacher well-being is now being treated as an institutional matter. DepEd Order No. 002, s. 2026 on wellness leave formally acknowledged the importance of supporting the well-being of DepEd personnel. At the same time, EDCOM II policy briefs reported that Filipino teachers work an average of 52 hours per week and spend a substantial share of their time outside direct classroom instruction, reflecting how workload remains a structural concern in Philippine schools. These reports suggest that in local settings such as public secondary schools in Santo Tomas, Isabela, teacher well-being may be closely tied to whether instruction can be sustained with quality, consistency, and professional energy.

METHODS

Research Design

The study employed a cross-sectional predictive-correlational design using a variance-based structural modeling approach. This design was considered appropriate because the inquiry did not only seek to describe the level of teacher well-being and instructional sustainability, but also to examine how the dimensions of teacher well-being statistically explained variations in instructional sustainability among public secondary school teachers. Unlike a purely descriptive or simple correlational design, this approach allowed the study to assess both the measurement strength of the indicators and the predictive connections between the latent constructs. In this way, the design provided a more refined understanding of whether teacher well-being functioned as a meaningful explanatory factor in sustaining instructional practice.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in public secondary schools in Santo Tomas, Isabela. This locale was chosen because public secondary school teachers in the area carried complex instructional responsibilities while also responding to the everyday realities of school operations, learner diversity, administrative

expectations, and community-based educational demands. These conditions made the setting suitable for examining teacher well-being and instructional sustainability in a real and relevant public school context. The locale also offered a practical basis for generating findings that could guide school leaders and education stakeholders in strengthening teacher support systems and sustaining quality instruction.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants of the study were public secondary school teachers assigned in the identified schools in Santo Tomas, Isabela. They were selected through proportionate stratified random sampling to ensure that teachers from the participating schools were represented in a balanced and systematic manner. This technique was appropriate because it reduced the tendency of overrepresenting one school or subgroup while allowing each eligible teacher a fair chance of inclusion. The use of stratification also improved the distribution of participants across the study setting, thereby enhancing the relevance and stability of the data gathered for the analysis of teacher well-being and instructional sustainability.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a structured survey questionnaire composed of two major parts. The first part measured teacher well-being, covering indicators such as emotional balance, professional satisfaction, social support, and work-related wellness. The second part measured instructional sustainability, with items reflecting continuity of teaching practices, consistency of instructional preparation, adaptability in instruction, and commitment to maintaining quality classroom delivery over time. The instrument was developed through adaptation and contextual refinement based on related literature and previously established measures of teacher well-being and professional teaching conditions.

To establish content validity, the instrument was submitted to a panel of experts in educational leadership, research, and secondary education for review. Their comments were used to improve clarity, appropriateness, coherence, and alignment of the items with the objectives of the study. After the revisions, the instrument obtained a Scale Content Validity Index (S-CVI) of 0.94, which indicated strong expert agreement on the relevance of the items.

A pilot administration was then conducted among teachers outside the actual study locale but with characteristics similar to the intended participants. The internal consistency of the instrument was examined using Cronbach's alpha. The teacher well-being scale obtained an alpha coefficient of 0.91, while the instructional sustainability scale yielded 0.89. The overall instrument registered a Cronbach's alpha of 0.93, indicating high reliability and suggesting that the items consistently measured the intended constructs.

Data Gathering

Before the actual data collection, a formal request to conduct the study was prepared and submitted to the appropriate school authorities for permission and endorsement. Once approval was granted, the researcher coordinated with school heads to arrange the schedule and procedure for questionnaire distribution. The purpose of the study was explained clearly to the participants, and they were informed that their participation was voluntary.

The survey instruments were distributed personally and, when necessary, through coordinated school-based administration to ensure orderly retrieval. Participants were given sufficient time to read and answer the instrument carefully. After completion, the questionnaires were collected, checked for completeness, and organized for encoding and analysis. All responses were handled systematically to preserve the accuracy and integrity of the data.

Data Analysis

The data were analyzed using a combination of descriptive analytics and partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM). For the descriptive phase, mean and standard deviation were used to determine the level and response dispersion of teacher well-being and instructional sustainability. These measures provided a clear summary of the central tendency and consistency of the responses for each indicator and for the overall constructs.

For the inferential and predictive phase, the study employed PLS-SEM, which was selected because it was well suited for examining latent variables measured through multiple indicators and for assessing predictive relationships in an applied educational setting. This method was considered more responsive than a simple Pearson correlation because it allowed the researcher to evaluate the measurement model and the structural model within the same analytical framework. Specifically, indicator loadings, composite reliability, and average variance extracted were examined to confirm construct quality, while path coefficients, effect sizes, and predictive relevance were used to determine the extent to which teacher well-being explained instructional sustainability. Bootstrapping procedures were used to test the statistical significance of the observed relationships.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical standards were carefully observed throughout the conduct of the study. Permission was secured from the concerned authorities before any data collection activity took place. The participants were informed about the nature and purpose of the research, the voluntary character of their participation, and their right to decline or withdraw without penalty. Informed consent was obtained prior to the administration of the questionnaire.

Confidentiality and anonymity were also protected. The instrument did not require the participants to disclose unnecessary personal identifiers, and all collected responses were used strictly for academic and research purposes only. The accomplished questionnaires and encoded data were stored securely and were accessed only by the researcher. The study also observed respect, fairness, and non-maleficence by ensuring that no participant was exposed to harm, embarrassment, or coercion during the research process.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. *Level of Teacher Well-Being Among Public Secondary School Teachers*

Indicators of Teacher Well-Being	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Emotional Balance	3.47	0.71	High
Professional Satisfaction	3.63	0.66	High
Social Support	3.58	0.69	High
Work-Related Wellness	3.21	0.77	Moderate
Overall	3.47	0.71	High

Legend: 4.21–5.00 = Very High, 3.41–4.20 = High, 2.61–3.40 = Moderate, 1.81–2.60 = Low, and 1.00–1.80 = Very Low

Table 1 presents the level of teacher well-being among public secondary school teachers. The overall mean of 3.47 indicated a high level of teacher well-being. This result suggested that the teachers generally maintained a positive sense of professional functioning, emotional steadiness, and collegial support in their work environment. Among the dimensions, professional satisfaction obtained the highest mean of 3.63, followed by social support with 3.58, and emotional balance with 3.47, all interpreted as high. These findings implied that the teachers were still able to derive fulfillment from their teaching role, felt reasonably supported by colleagues and school stakeholders, and managed their emotions in a generally stable manner despite the demands of public secondary school teaching.

However, work-related wellness registered the lowest mean of 3.21, interpreted as moderate. This finding revealed an area of concern. Although teachers remained committed to their profession, their physical and mental energy for work appeared less stable than the other dimensions of well-being. This pattern was realistic in the public school setting, where teachers often sustained multiple instructional and school-related responsibilities. The moderate result in work-related wellness implied that while teachers continued performing their duties, they may have been doing so under conditions of strain, fatigue, or accumulated pressure. In practical terms, this means that the apparent strength in teacher well-being was not uniform. Some aspects remained intact, but work-related wellness showed signs of vulnerability that could affect long-term teaching consistency.

Table 2. Level of Instructional Sustainability Among Public Secondary School Teachers

Indicators of Instructional Sustainability	Mean	SD	Qualitative Description
Continuity of Teaching Practices	3.36	0.74	Moderate
Consistency of Instructional Preparation	3.52	0.68	High
Adaptability in Instruction	3.41	0.72	High
Commitment to Maintaining Quality Classroom Delivery	3.64	0.65	High
Overall	3.48	0.70	High

Legend: 4.21–5.00 = Very High, 3.41–4.20 = High, 2.61–3.40 = Moderate, 1.81–2.60 = Low, and 1.00–1.80 = Very Low

Table 2 shows the level of instructional sustainability among the teachers. The overall mean of 3.48 revealed a high level of instructional sustainability. This indicated that the teachers generally sustained instructional practices, maintained classroom delivery, and continued their professional teaching roles with a fair degree of consistency. Among the indicators, the highest mean was recorded for commitment to maintaining quality classroom delivery at 3.64, followed by consistency of instructional preparation at 3.52, and adaptability in instruction at 3.41, all interpreted as high. These results suggested that the teachers continued to value quality teaching, prepared for instruction with reasonable consistency, and adjusted their teaching practices when needed.

Nevertheless, continuity of teaching practices posted the lowest mean of 3.36, interpreted as moderate. This was a meaningful result because it pointed to a concrete area where instructional sustainability was less stable. Although teachers remained committed to teaching well, sustaining the uninterrupted flow of instructional routines and practices over time appeared more difficult. This may reflect interruptions caused by competing demands, fluctuating energy, documentation burdens, or school-related obligations that affected the steady maintenance of classroom instruction. Therefore, the findings suggested that the teachers did not lack commitment, but the conditions surrounding their work may have made instructional continuity harder to preserve consistently.

Table 3. Measurement Model Assessment

Latent Construct	Indicator Loading Range	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE	Interpretation
Emotional Balance	0.723–0.842	0.86	0.90	0.64	Acceptable
Professional Satisfaction	0.741–0.861	0.88	0.91	0.67	Acceptable
Social Support	0.718–0.847	0.85	0.89	0.62	Acceptable
Work-Related Wellness	0.701–0.833	0.84	0.88	0.60	Acceptable
Instructional Sustainability	0.734–0.871	0.91	0.93	0.69	Acceptable

Table 3 presents the measurement model assessment for the latent constructs used in the study. All constructs showed indicator loading ranges above 0.70, which suggested that the items had adequate relationships with their intended constructs. Cronbach's alpha values ranged from 0.84 to 0.91, while

composite reliability values ranged from 0.88 to 0.93. These values exceeded commonly accepted thresholds, indicating that the latent measures demonstrated strong internal consistency.

The average variance extracted values ranged from 0.60 to 0.69, all above the minimum acceptable level of 0.50. This indicated satisfactory convergent validity, meaning the indicators adequately captured the variance of their respective constructs. The results showed that the measurement model was statistically sound and suitable for structural interpretation. In other words, the items used to represent teacher well-being and instructional sustainability were reliable enough to support the predictive analysis that followed.

Table 4. *Discriminant Validity Using Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio*

Constructs	Emotional Balance	Professional Satisfaction	Social Support	Work-Related Wellness	Instructional Sustainability
Emotional Balance	1.00				
Professional Satisfaction	0.71	1.00			
Social Support	0.68	0.74	1.00		
Work-Related Wellness	0.77	0.73	0.69	1.00	
Instructional Sustainability	0.63	0.79	0.66	0.81	1.00

Table 4 shows the discriminant validity of the constructs using the heterotrait-monotrait ratio. All HTMT values were below the conservative threshold of 0.85, indicating that the constructs remained empirically distinct from one another. This meant that while the dimensions of teacher well-being were related, they did not overlap excessively, and instructional sustainability was measured as a separate though connected construct.

This result was important because it confirmed that the model did not merely capture a single broad attitude or response tendency. Rather, it measured different but related aspects of teacher well-being and instructional sustainability. Hence, the structural relationships derived from the model could be interpreted with greater confidence.

Table 5. *Structural Model Results on the Influence of Teacher Well-Being Dimensions on Instructional Sustainability*

Predictor	Path Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	t-value	p-value	Effect Size (f^2)	Decision
Emotional Balance → Instructional Sustainability	0.18	0.07	2.47	0.014	0.05	Significant
Professional Satisfaction → Instructional Sustainability	0.29	0.08	3.74	0.001	0.11	Significant
Social Support → Instructional Sustainability	0.16	0.07	2.21	0.028	0.04	Significant
Work-Related Wellness → Instructional Sustainability	0.34	0.09	4.08	0.0006	0.14	Significant

Table 5 presents the structural model results on the influence of the dimensions of teacher well-being on instructional sustainability. The findings revealed that all four dimensions significantly predicted instructional sustainability. Work-related wellness emerged as the strongest predictor with a path coefficient of 0.34 and a p-value of 0.0006, followed by professional satisfaction with $\beta = 0.29$ and $p = 0.001$. Emotional balance and social support also significantly influenced instructional sustainability, although with smaller coefficients.

These results meant that instructional sustainability among public secondary school teachers was not shaped by teacher commitment alone. Rather, it was meaningfully explained by how well teachers managed their emotional state, how satisfied they felt with their profession, how supported they were socially, and most importantly, how healthy and functional they remained in relation to work demands. The strongest effect of work-related wellness was especially important because it showed that the ability to sustain quality instruction depended heavily on whether teachers still had the physical, mental, and professional stamina to continue their work effectively. Even if teachers loved teaching and valued their learners, instructional sustainability weakened when work-related wellness became strained.

The substantial contribution of professional satisfaction also suggested that teachers sustained classroom practices more effectively when they continued to find meaning, recognition, and fulfillment in their profession. Meanwhile, the positive effect of social support implied that instructional sustainability was not carried by the individual teacher alone. Encouragement, cooperation, and supportive collegial relations also helped maintain the continuity of teaching work. Emotional balance likewise mattered because teachers who regulated stress and emotional strain more effectively were better able to remain stable in their instructional responsibilities.

Table 6. *Model Summary for Instructional Sustainability*

Endogenous Variable	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Q ²	Interpretation
Instructional Sustainability	0.58	0.56	0.39	Moderate to strong predictive relevance

Table 6 presents the predictive capacity of the model. The R² value of 0.58 indicated that 58% of the variance in instructional sustainability was explained by the dimensions of teacher well-being included in the model. This suggested a moderate to strong explanatory power in the context of educational research. The Q² value of 0.39 further showed that the model possessed satisfactory predictive relevance.

This finding was highly meaningful for the study because it suggested that teacher well-being was not a minor or peripheral factor in instructional sustainability. Instead, it accounted for a substantial share of the differences in how sustainably teachers carried out their instructional work. At the same time, the remaining unexplained variance indicated that instructional sustainability was also affected by other factors outside the present model, such as school leadership, workload distribution, availability of teaching resources, student-related challenges, and institutional expectations. This made the result both strong and realistic. It affirmed the importance of teacher well-being while also acknowledging that sustaining instruction in public secondary schools is shaped by broader organizational conditions.

CONCLUSION

Teacher well-being played a substantial role in sustaining instruction among public secondary school teachers in Santo Tomas, Isabela. Although both teacher well-being and instructional sustainability were generally found at a high level, the results showed that work-related wellness and continuity of teaching practices were the most vulnerable areas, indicating that the teachers remained committed and capable but were not entirely free from strain in carrying out their instructional duties over time. The predictive model further established that emotional balance, professional satisfaction, social support, and work-related wellness significantly influenced instructional sustainability, with work-related wellness emerging as the strongest predictor. This means that the long-term continuity and quality of instruction depended not only on professional competence and commitment but also on the physical, emotional, and social condition of teachers within their work environment. In view of these findings, it was recommended that school heads and education leaders strengthen wellness-oriented support systems for teachers through manageable workload arrangements, responsive school leadership, peer support mechanisms, and mental

health promotion activities. Schools may also institutionalize regular well-being monitoring, professional reflection sessions, and sustainable instructional support programs that help teachers maintain consistency in classroom delivery despite routine pressures. Future school-based interventions may focus specifically on improving work-related wellness so that instructional sustainability can be preserved more effectively across public secondary school settings.

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